

General Readme

General remarks:

To conduct a test with adults using the Multilingual Assessment Instrument for Narratives (MAIN), you should consider the following:

You will need the current and official version of the MAIN protocol (for testing children), which is available in various languages via the MAIN website. There you will find necessary explanations about the procedure and the assessment including the scoring grid.

In addition, you will need the instructions for testing with adults, as a supplement in the case of testing adults. Everything that is not listed there is identical to the procedure for testing children, including the assessment procedure. This is to ensure the greatest possible comparability and should therefore be observed. The instructions are currently available in Russian, German and Polish. In case you need another language, see if this language exists for testing children and use this as a basis to create the adult version. For this, please orientate yourself on the German version for adults (this is the most comprehensive one and served as a basis for translation into Russian and Polish, which differ to a certain degree) and adjust the corresponding passages. Please note the necessary form of polite address and the wording for retelling the story. This differs from the children's version and should be adapted accordingly.

And finally, you need the PPT-slides/the pictorial material, which are available via the MAIN website.

In case you want the test person to tell more than one story, adjust the instructions so that you present the general information about the process only once. For the second telling, you can then refer to what has already been said.

Before testing:

Familiarize yourself with the material in advance, click through the presentation/the link provided once and make sure that all animations are set and displayed correctly, do a test run and adjust your remarks to the order of the slides/the animations in the link. Be sure that everything runs on your computer.

Before you start testing, make sure that all technical devices are in order. If you are using a laptop, please check that it's connected to the power supply or have the charger ready. Check that there is an electrical outlet nearby. The video and the audio should be working. Make sure that you record the entire session, including the answers to the comprehension questions. The camera and audio should be tested prior to the experiment.

Make sure that you have thoroughly familiarized yourself with the story protocols and the instructions.

Administer the assessment according to the instructions. No help in answering the questions, telling or retelling or performing any other actions during the experiment is allowed.

While testing:

The test person should be sitting in front of the screen, so that the video is directed at him/her directly. Explain the context of the study: name, that the test was developed for children, and that it is about telling a story and answering some questions about it.